

Syntheses of Tetrahydrobenzothiazole Derivatives as Potential Antibacterial Compounds

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New compounds having thiazole nucleus incorporated with β -lactam, azomethine and thiazolidinone moieties were prepared. The thiazole nucleus under study was 2-substituted-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole.

SCHIFF bases are well-known to have pronounced biological activities^{1,2}; some have shown anti-carcinogenic properties. Many thiazolidinones have shown anaesthetic anticonvulsant and anti-tubercular properties^{3,4}. Antibiotics containing β -lactam ring structure constitute dominating class of agents currently employed for chemotherapy of bacterial infection⁵. Therefore, it was decided to synthesise the above classes of compounds with incorporation of another active moiety in order to enhance the present level of activity. The moiety under study was 2,3,7,8-tetrahydrobenzothiazole.

Experimental

1-(4',5',6',7'-Tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-2-alkyl/arylhydrazones (1a): The compounds were prepared by condensing substituted-thiosemicarbazones with 2-bromocyclohexanone.

1-(4',5',6',7'-Tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-3-chloro-4-alkyl/arylazetidiones (1b). *General procedure*: The monochloroacetyl chloride (11.3 g, 0.1 mol) was added with stirring to a mixture of 1-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-2-alkyl/arylhydrazones (0.05 mol) and triethylamine (10.1 g, 0.1 mol) in dry benzene (250 cm³). The stirring was continued for 5 h at 40–50° and then left overnight. The triethylamine hydrochloride precipitate was filtered, washed with benzene and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure. The amide was collected and crystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

2-Amino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole (2a): It was prepared⁷ by condensing 2-bromocyclohexanone and thiourea.

2-Alkyl/arylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazoles (2b). *General procedure*: A mixture of carbonyl compound (0.1 mol), 2-amino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole (15.4 g, 0.1 mol) and catalytic quantity of piperidine in dry benzene (100 cm³) was refluxed using Dean and Stark water-separator till 1.8 cm³ (0.1 mol) of water separated out. The product which separated on cooling was filtered and crystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

2-Alkyl/arylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazoles (3a): The compounds were prepared as described above for 2b.

2-Alkyl/aryl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinones (3b). *General procedure*: A mixture of 2-alkyl/arylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole (0.1 mol) and thioglycolic acid (9.2 g, 0.1 mol) was refluxed using a Dean and Stark water-separator till 1.8 cm³ (0.1 mol) of water separated out. The reaction mixture was cooled and then washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from ethanol (Table 3).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Compd.	M.p. °C	Appearance	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1.	1-(2'-Amino-4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-yl)-3-chloro-4-dimethylazetidione	125	Buff coloured crystals	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ OS	50.49 (50.49)	5.67 (5.64)	14.75 (14.70)
2.	1-(2'-Amino-4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-yl)-3-chloro-4-methylethylazetidione	141	Buff coloured crystals	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ OS	52.12 (52.08)	6.12 (6.051)	14.11 (14.09)
3.	1-(2'-Amino-4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-yl)-3-chloro-4-methylisobutylazetidione	143	Buff coloured crystals	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ OS	55.01 (54.95)	6.79 (6.76)	12.91 (12.82)
4.	1-(2'-Amino-4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-yl)-3-chloro-4-cyclohexylazetidione	135	Yellow crystals	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ OS	54.99 (55.29)	6.01 (6.19)	12.90 (12.90)
5.	1-(2'-Amino-4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-yl)-3-chloro-4-ethylazetidione	133	Brown crystals	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ OS	50.59 (50.43)	5.71 (5.64)	14.81 (14.70)
6.	1-(2'-Amino-4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-yl)-3-chloro-4-benzylazetidione	150	Brown crystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ OS	57.69 (57.57)	4.92 (4.83)	12.67 (12.59)
7.	1-(2'-Amino-4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-yl)-3-chloro-4-p-chlorobenzylazetidione	151	Buff coloured crystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS	52.22 (52.10)	4.09 (4.11)	11.49 (11.41)
8.	1-(2'-Amino-4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-yl)-3-chloro-4-p-methoxybenzylazetidione	140	Buff coloured crystals	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	56.00 (56.12)	4.89 (4.99)	11.47 (11.55)
9.	1-(2'-Amino-4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-yl)-3-chloro-4-p-methylbenzylazetidione	142	Buff coloured crystals	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ OS	50.70 (50.70)	5.32 (5.22)	12.11 (12.08)

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Compd.	M.p. °C	Appearance	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1.	2-Dimethylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole	209	White crystals	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	61.89 (61.82)	7.39 (7.26)	14.45 (14.47)
2.	2-Methylethylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole	211	Buff coloured crystals	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ S	63.22 (63.42)	7.59 (7.74)	13.54 (13.44)
3.	2-Methylisobutylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole	205	Buff coloured crystals	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ S	66.32 (66.06)	8.61 (8.53)	11.75 (11.85)
4.	2-Cyclohexylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole	207	White crystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ S	66.69 (66.63)	7.91 (7.73)	11.55 (11.95)
5.	2-Ethylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole	198	Buff coloured crystals	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	61.62 (61.82)	7.60 (7.26)	14.39 (14.42)
6.	2-Benzylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole	108	Yellow crystals	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	69.25 (69.36)	5.72 (5.82)	11.39 (11.56)
7.	2-p-Chlorobenzylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole	151	Yellow crystals	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ClN ₂ S	60.42 (60.75)	4.39 (4.73)	10.40 (10.12)
8.	2-p-Methoxybenzylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole	207	Yellowish brown crystals	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	66.29 (66.15)	5.85 (5.92)	10.38 (10.29)
9.	2-p-Methylbenzylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole	112	Yellow crystals	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ S	70.31 (70.28)	6.31 (6.28)	10.86 (10.93)

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Compd.	M.p. °C	Appearance	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1.	2-Dimethyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone	212	White crystals	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS ₂	53.39 (53.70)	6.32 (6.00)	10.11 (10.44)
2.	2-Methyl ethyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone	156	Yellowish white powder	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS ₂	55.11 (55.28)	6.33 (6.42)	9.72 (9.92)
3.	2-Methyl isobutyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone	166	White powder	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ OS ₂	58.11 (58.08)	7.35 (7.14)	9.21 (9.02)
4.	2-Cyclohexyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone	225	White powder	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ OS ₂	58.21 (58.41)	6.26 (6.54)	9.20 (9.09)
5.	2-Ethyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone	210	White powder	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS ₂	53.75 (53.70)	6.23 (6.00)	10.59 (10.44)
6.	2-Benzyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone	136	Yellow powder	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS ₂	60.71 (60.73)	5.01 (5.10)	8.71 (8.85)
7.	2-p-Chlorobenzyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone	132	Yellow crystals	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS ₂	54.61 (54.77)	4.20 (4.31)	7.62 (7.98)
8.	2-p-Methoxybenzyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone	125	Yellow powder	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	56.72 (58.94)	5.10 (5.23)	8.19 (8.09)
9.	2-p-Methylbenzyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone	130	Buff coloured powder	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS ₂	61.91 (61.79)	5.62 (5.49)	8.61 (8.48)

TABLE 4—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Compd.	M.p. °C	Appearance	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1.	2-Dimethyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone-5-acetic acid	117	Yellow powder	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	51.33 (51.51)	5.32 (5.55)	8.41 (8.58)
2.	2-Methyl ethyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone-5-acetic acid	127	Light yellow powder	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	52.63 (52.92)	5.79 (5.92)	8.11 (8.23)
3.	2-Methyl isobutyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone-5-acetic acid	120	Yellow powder	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	55.59 (55.41)	6.71 (6.56)	7.32 (7.60)
4.	2-Cyclohexyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone-5-acetic acid	164	White powder	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	55.60 (55.71)	6.21 (6.05)	7.49 (7.64)
5.	2-Ethyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone-5-acetic acid	110	Yellow powder	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	51.71 (51.51)	5.73 (5.55)	8.25 (8.50)
6.	2-Benzyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone-5-acetic acid	191	Yellow powder	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	57.51 (57.73)	4.77 (4.84)	7.32 (7.48)
7.	2-p-Chlorobenzyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone-5-acetic acid	120	Yellow powder	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₃ S ₂	52.98 (52.87)	4.30 (4.19)	6.77 (6.05)
8.	2-p-Methoxybenzyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone-5-acetic acid	101	Yellow powder	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	56.32 (56.41)	4.89 (4.98)	6.83 (6.93)
9.	2-p-Methylbenzyl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone-5-acetic acid	108	Buff coloured powder	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	58.79 (58.74)	5.23 (5.19)	7.42 (7.21)

2-Alkyl/arylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazoles (4a): The compounds were prepared as described above for 2b.

2-Alkyl/aryl-3-(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydrobenzothiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone-5-acetic acids (4b). *General procedure*: A mixture of 2-alkyl/arylidenamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazole (15.4 g, 0.1 mol) and mercaptosuccinic acid (15.0 g, 0.1 mol) was refluxed using a Dean and Stark water-separator till 1.8 cm³ (0.1 mol) of water was separated. The reaction mixture was cooled and then extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution. The bicarbonate extract was acidified with hydrochloric acid and the resulting solid was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from ethanol (Table 4).

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References

1. E. M. HODNETT and W. I. DUNN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 768.
2. H. J. BILLMANN and R. L. SCHMIDGALL, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1920, **59**, 1191.
3. A. R. SURREY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 3354.
4. H. D. TROUTMAN and L. M. LONG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3436.
5. R. F. DOERGES, "Wilson and Gisrold's Textbook of Organic Medicinal and Pharmaceutical Chemistry", 8th. ed., J. B. Lippincott Company, 1982, p. 225.
6. A. K. MORRIS, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, **61**, 12007.
7. C. C. HURD and H. L. WEHRMEISTER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 4007.
8. B. DASH, M. PATRA and P. K. MAHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 521.